

2_Notebook_modeling

May 5, 2022

1 Notebook 2: Hydrus-1D modeling

supporting the manuscript: **Sensitivity of evapotranspiration and seepage to elevated atmospheric CO_2 from lysimeter experiments in a montane grassland**

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1.0.1 The supporting Notebook is structured as follows.

1. Import observation data
2. Estimating potential evaporation under elevated CO_2
3. Create input for Hydrus-1D
4. Estimate stomatal resistance (r_l) for each lysimeter
5. Calibrate/parameterize the stomatal resistance model
6. Water stress

The analysis is conducted on the ambient (reference) lysimeter (L_aCO_2) and the CO_2 enriched lysimeter (L_eCO_2)

```
[1]: import numpy as np
import pandas as pd
import os
import pylab
import phydrus as ps
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import hydrostats.metrics as hm
from lmfit import Model, Parameters, fit_report, minimize
from spotpy.objectivefunctions import nashsutcliffe, kge
from scipy import stats
import pyet
import phydrus
from statsmodels.stats.stattools import durbin_watson
import spotpy
from utils import *

ps.show_versions()
```

Python version: 3.8.11 (default, Aug 6 2021, 09:57:55) [MSC v.1916 64 bit (AMD64)]

Numpy version: 1.20.3

Pandas version: 1.4.1
Phydrus version: 0.3.0b
Matplotlib version: 3.5.1

```
[2]: params = {
    "font.family": "Arial",
    "legend.fontsize": "8",
    "patch.linewidth": "10",
    "lines.linewidth": "0.4",
    "axes.labelsize": "6",
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    "xtick.labelsize": "6",
    "ytick.labelsize": "6",
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    "ytick.major.size": "2",
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    "ytick.major.width": "0.3",
    "xtick.major.pad": "2",
    "ytick.major.pad": "2",
    "xtick.direction": "in",
    "ytick.direction": "in",
    "figure.subplot.wspace": "0.1",
    "axes.labelpad": "3",
    "axes.titlepad": "8",
    "axes.linewidth": "0.4",
    "xtick.minor.size": "1.5",
    "xtick.minor.width": "0.15",
    "hatch.linewidth": "0.2",
}
figw_1c = 8.5 # maximum width for 1 column
figw_2c = 17.5 # maximum width for 2 columns
pylab.rcParams.update(params)
```

```
[3]: def w_lst(evaluation, simulation, weights):
    """Weighted least squares"""
    lst = sum(weights * (evaluation - simulation) ** 2)
    return lst
```

2 1. Import data

```
[4]: meteo = pd.read_csv("data\meteo_d_2015_2020.csv",
    index_col=0, parse_dates=True)
meteo.describe()
```

```
[4]:
```

	Tmean_ [C]	Tmax_ [C]	Tmin_ [C]	RHmean_ [%]	RHmax_ [%]	\
count	2192.000000	2192.000000	2192.000000	2192.000000	2192.000000	
mean	8.421905	14.193431	3.483485	79.962612	96.879106	

std	7.913800	9.381580	7.164197	10.783647	4.063225
min	-12.955556	-9.800000	-19.400000	42.576389	62.000000
25%	1.740625	5.900000	-1.625000	72.666667	97.000000
50%	8.680208	14.400000	3.300000	80.861111	98.000000
75%	15.078299	21.600000	9.800000	88.385417	99.000000
max	25.029861	35.000000	17.800000	99.215278	100.000000

	RHmin_ [%]	wind_2m_ [m/s]	solar_ [MJ/m2d]	Precip_ [mm/d]	ET0_ [mm]
count	2192.000000	2192.000000	2192.000000	2192.000000	2192.000000
mean	53.704836	1.349244	11.673437	2.967153	1.837890
std	17.446168	0.541800	7.821675	6.809449	1.668232
min	11.000000	0.383333	0.610200	0.000000	-0.153171
25%	40.000000	0.986806	4.970550	0.000000	0.399060
50%	51.000000	1.311111	9.714300	0.000000	1.292689
75%	65.000000	1.625000	17.860650	2.800000	3.097603
max	99.000000	4.738889	30.405000	98.300000	6.955875

```
[5]: lysimeters_h = pd.read_csv("data\swfluxes_2015_2020.csv",
                                index_col=0, parse_dates=True)
lysimeters = lysimeters_h.resample("d").sum()
lysimeters.describe()
```

```
[5]:
```

	ET-L2	ET-L0	P-L2	P-L0	Seep-L2 \
count	2192.000000	2192.000000	2192.000000	2192.000000	2192.000000
mean	1.738351	1.894596	3.128399	3.104913	1.479133
std	1.650723	1.842255	6.528876	6.530643	2.696123
min	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000
25%	0.410000	0.430000	0.080000	0.060000	0.000000
50%	1.100000	1.160000	0.460000	0.370000	0.660000
75%	2.800000	2.980000	3.112500	3.085000	1.790000
max	7.930000	9.390000	80.990000	81.840000	40.820000

	Seep-L0
count	2192.000000
mean	1.300036
std	2.695887
min	0.000000
25%	0.000000
50%	0.420000
75%	1.462500
max	41.950000

```
[6]: sensors_h = pd.read_csv("data\sensors_2015_2020.csv",
                                index_col=0, parse_dates=True)
sensors = sensors_h.resample("d").mean()
sensors.describe()
```

```
[6]:
```

	SWC_10_L2	SWC_10_L0	SWC_30_L2	SWC_30_L0	SWC_50_L2	\
count	2192.000000	2192.000000	2192.000000	2192.000000	2192.000000	
mean	40.027842	34.495601	36.401426	34.171323	32.976395	
std	4.938139	5.318684	2.108405	3.061848	1.716598	
min	24.504167	19.571250	28.565833	22.788333	26.055833	
25%	36.774271	30.913854	35.358542	32.710000	32.307812	
50%	40.537292	34.105208	36.741667	34.585000	33.250417	
75%	43.615833	38.546979	37.816667	36.159896	34.081250	
max	51.315000	46.256250	40.501250	41.828333	37.036250	

	SWC_50_L0	WP_10_L2	WP_10_L0	WP_30_L2	WP_30_L0	\
count	2192.000000	2192.000000	2192.000000	2192.000000	2192.000000	
mean	29.257373	-128.232117	-181.699075	-154.264592	-176.355999	
std	3.018442	174.485309	206.737959	152.585041	185.852035	
min	19.371250	-772.836667	-846.446667	-820.655417	-831.310833	
25%	28.180208	-160.687917	-257.380833	-158.466667	-195.824792	
50%	29.897917	-51.264375	-91.601458	-98.451250	-100.258750	
75%	31.048333	-23.243229	-36.158854	-67.101042	-61.088854	
max	36.728750	37.653750	5.735417	0.000000	5.429167	

	WP_50_L2	WP_50_L0	WP_140_L2	WP_140_L0
count	2192.000000	2192.000000	2192.000000	2192.000000
mean	-150.467806	-178.827555	-79.780485	-86.275535
std	146.402041	176.910660	56.724735	60.368238
min	-802.100833	-818.312500	-287.484167	-292.153333
25%	-143.942292	-181.896146	-65.338021	-87.572188
50%	-96.571250	-104.465000	-56.319167	-56.227708
75%	-70.063958	-74.987813	-55.539687	-55.546979
max	0.000000	0.000000	0.472500	16.012917

```
[7]: stemp = (pd.read_csv("data\stemp_2015_2020.csv",
                        index_col=0, parse_dates=True).resample("d").mean())
stemp.head()
```

```
[7]:
```

	temp_5cm_L2	temp_140cm_L2
2015-01-01	NaN	4.023056
2015-01-02	NaN	3.971528
2015-01-03	NaN	3.939722
2015-01-04	NaN	3.911319
2015-01-05	NaN	3.853750

```
[8]: print(stemp.loc["2017-1-1",:])
```

```
temp_5cm_L2    -0.400667
temp_140cm_L2    3.180139
Name: 2017-01-01 00:00:00, dtype: float64
```

```
[9]: phenology = pd.read_csv("data\\crop_phenology_2015_2020.csv",
                             index_col=0, parse_dates=True)
phenology.describe()
```

```
[9]:
```

	LAI_fs_L2	LAI_fs_L0	LAI_mix_L2	LAI_mix_L0	ch_L2	\
count	2192.000000	2192.000000	2192.000000	2192.000000	2192.000000	
mean	1.314868	1.293589	1.318831	1.301974	0.161596	
std	1.151674	1.166390	1.181779	1.198689	0.120984	
min	0.200000	0.200000	0.200000	0.200000	0.100000	
25%	0.500000	0.500000	0.500000	0.500000	0.100000	
50%	0.500000	0.500000	0.500000	0.500000	0.100000	
75%	2.378335	2.364578	2.350515	2.236273	0.185229	
max	6.477000	5.542900	6.477000	5.542900	0.842500	

	ch_L0	fspec_raw_L2	fspec_raw_L0	accu_raw_L2	accu_raw_L0
count	2192.000000	68.000000	68.000000	114.000000	114.000000
mean	0.176174	2.877604	2.854535	2.710058	2.975000
std	0.140639	0.761411	0.813038	1.298183	1.391830
min	0.100000	1.369200	0.731500	0.193333	0.440000
25%	0.100000	2.363075	2.476025	1.730000	1.900833
50%	0.100000	2.851700	2.818150	2.798333	3.096667
75%	0.214531	3.217450	3.258750	3.768333	3.835000
max	0.922500	6.477000	5.542900	5.893333	6.466667

```
[10]: co2 = pd.read_csv("data\co2_levels_2018_2020.csv",
                        index_col=0, parse_dates=True)
co2.head()
```

```
[10]:
```

	L2	L0	flag	TAR_20	TAR_30
2018-04-11	545.959187	430.295218	0	0.775330	0.867841
2018-04-12	424.168573	424.168573	1	NaN	NaN
2018-04-13	509.559142	426.295190	0	0.730769	0.818681
2018-04-14	623.657269	436.884341	0	0.803526	0.884131
2018-04-15	697.125982	446.907521	0	0.725971	0.820041

```
[11]: periods = pd.read_csv("data\\veg_err_period.csv",
                             index_col=0, parse_dates=True)
periods.loc["2020-9-23", "L2_error"]=1
periods.head()
```

```
[11]:
```

	L2_error	L0_error	smai_L0	smai_L2	wstress_smai_L0	\
2017-01-01	0	0	0.921152	0.686732		0
2017-01-02	0	0	0.781079	0.535816		0
2017-01-03	0	0	0.639634	0.409326		0
2017-01-04	0	0	0.538602	0.338492		0
2017-01-05	0	0	0.487088	0.301679		0

	wstress_smai_L2	veg_period
2017-01-01	0	0
2017-01-02	0	0
2017-01-03	0	0
2017-01-04	0	0
2017-01-05	0	0

3 2. Estimating potential evaporation under elevated CO_2

```
[12]: lat = 47.4935 * np.pi / 180 # 47.4935° N
      elevation = 700
```

```
[13]: def et_sc1(r_l, lai, croph, srs, co2, s1="2016"):
      pe = pyet.pm(
          meteo.loc[s1:, "Tmean_[C]"],
          meteo.loc[s1:, "wind_2m_[m/s]"],
          rs=meteo.loc[s1:, "solar_[MJ/m2d]"],
          elevation=elevation,
          lat=lat,
          rhmax=meteo.loc[s1:, "RHmax_[%]"],
          rhmin=meteo.loc[s1:, "RHmin_[%]"],
          tmax=meteo.loc[s1:, "Tmax_[C]"],
          tmin=meteo.loc[s1:, "Tmin_[C]"],
          lai=lai,
          croph=croph,
          r_l=r_l,
          srs=srs,
          a=1,
          b=0,
          co2=co2,
          lai_eff=0,
          ra_method=2,
      )
      return pe
```

```
[14]: # Co2 data
      co2_c2 = co2.loc["2018":, "L2"]
      co2_c2 = co2_c2.reindex(pd.date_range("2016-1-1", "2020-12-31"))
      co2_c2["2016":"2017"] = 696 # ambient CO2 + 300 ppm
```

```
[15]: et0 = meteo["ETO_[mm]"]
```

```
[16]: s1 = "2016"
      pe_L2_sr1 = et_sc1(63, phenology.loc[s1:, "LAI_mix_L2"], phenology.loc[s1:, "ch_L2"], 0.002, co2_c2, s1,)
```

```

pe_L2_amb = et_sc1(78, phenology.loc[s1:, "LAI_mix_L2"], phenology.loc[s1:,
↳"ch_L2"], 0.002, 300, s1)
pe_L0_amb = et_sc1(78, phenology.loc[s1:, "LAI_mix_L0"], phenology.loc[s1:,
↳"ch_L0"], 0.002, 300, s1)
pe_L0_srl = et_sc1(63, phenology.loc[s1:, "LAI_mix_L0"], phenology.loc[s1:,
↳"ch_L0"], 0.002, 700, s1,)

```

```
[17]: print(pe_L2_srl.sum(), pe_L2_amb.sum(), pe_L0_srl.sum(), pe_L0_amb.sum())
```

2757.1077705077887 3201.0642101361764 2897.1116361854874 3207.010400514563

3.1 2.1 Replace PE with actual E outside the vegetation period and when meteo missing

```
[76]: veg_period_2017 = periods[periods["veg_period"] == 1].loc["2017"].index
non_veg_period = periods[periods["veg_period"] == 0].loc["2017:"].index
veg_period = periods[periods["veg_period"] == 1].loc["2017:"].index
```

```
[19]: l2_error = periods[periods["L2_error"] == 1].index
l0_error = periods[periods["L0_error"] == 1].index
```

```
[20]: eta_L2 = lysimeters["ET-L2"].copy()
eta_L0 = lysimeters["ET-L0"].copy()
prec_L0 = lysimeters["P-L0"].copy() / 10
prec_L2 = lysimeters["P-L2"].copy() / 10
seep_L0_lysi = lysimeters["Seep-L0"].copy() / 10
seep_L2_lysi = lysimeters["Seep-L2"].copy() / 10
# Error in the water budget
prec_L0.loc["2019-1":"2019-1"] = (meteo.loc["2019-1":"2019-1", "Precip_[mm/d]"].
↳copy() / 10)
prec_L2.loc["2019-1":"2019-1"] = (meteo.loc["2019-1":"2019-1", "Precip_[mm/d]"].
↳copy() / 10)
prec_L0.loc["2020-1":"2020-1"] = (meteo.loc["2019-1":"2019-1", "Precip_[mm/d]"].
↳copy() / 10)
prec_L2.loc["2020-1":"2020-1"] = (meteo.loc["2019-1":"2019-1", "Precip_[mm/d]"].
↳copy() / 10)
prec_L0.loc["2020-8":"2020-9"] = (meteo.loc["2020-8":"2020-9", "Precip_[mm/d]"].
↳copy() / 10)
prec_L2.loc["2020-8":"2020-9"] = (meteo.loc["2020-8":"2020-9", "Precip_[mm/d]"].
↳copy() / 10)
prec_L0.loc["2019-6":"2019-10"] = (meteo.loc["2019-6":"2019-10", "Precip_[mm/
↳d]").copy() / 10)
prec_L2.loc["2019-6":"2019-10"] = (meteo.loc["2019-6":"2019-10", "Precip_[mm/
↳d]").copy() / 10)

```

```
[21]: eta_L2[l2_error] = pe_L2_srl[l2_error]
eta_L0[l0_error] = pe_L0_amb[l0_error]
```

```
[22]: pe_L2_sim = pe_L2_srl
pe_L2_sim = pe_L2_sim.reindex(pd.date_range("2016-1-1", "2020-12-31"))
pe_L2_amb = pe_L2_amb.reindex(pd.date_range("2016-1-1", "2020-12-31"))
pe_L0_amb = pe_L0_amb.reindex(pd.date_range("2016-1-1", "2020-12-31"))
pe_L0_eco2 = pe_L0_srl
pe_L0_eco2 = pe_L0_srl.reindex(pd.date_range("2016-1-1", "2020-12-31"))

pe_L2_sim[non_veg_period] = eta_L2[non_veg_period] # replace PET with ETa in
↳non-vegetation period
pe_L2_amb[non_veg_period] = eta_L2[non_veg_period] # replace PET with ETa in
↳non-vegetation period
pe_L0_amb[non_veg_period] = eta_L0[non_veg_period] # replace PET with ETa in
↳non-vegetation period
pe_L0_eco2[non_veg_period] = eta_L0[non_veg_period] # replace PET with ETa in
↳non-vegetation period
```

4 3. Create input for Hydrus 1D

```
[23]: k = 0.6
rsoil_L2_sim = pe_L2_sim * np.exp(-k * phenology["LAI_mix_L2"]) / 10 # cm/d
rroot_L2_sim = pe_L2_sim * (1 - np.exp(-k * phenology["LAI_mix_L2"])) / 10 #
↳cm/d

rsoil_L2_amb = pe_L2_amb * np.exp(-k * phenology["LAI_mix_L2"]) / 10 # cm/d
rroot_L2_amb = pe_L2_amb * (1 - np.exp(-k * phenology["LAI_mix_L2"])) / 10 #
↳cm/d

rsoil_L2_lysi = eta_L2 * np.exp(-k * phenology["LAI_mix_L2"]) / 10 # cm/d
rroot_L2_lysi = eta_L2 * (1 - np.exp(-k * phenology["LAI_mix_L2"])) / 10 # cm/d

rsoil_L0_lysi = eta_L0 * np.exp(-k * phenology["LAI_mix_L0"]) / 10 # cm/d
rroot_L0_lysi = eta_L0 * (1 - np.exp(-k * phenology["LAI_mix_L0"])) / 10 # cm/d

rsoil_L0_amb = pe_L0_amb * np.exp(-k * phenology["LAI_mix_L0"]) / 10 # cm/d
rroot_L0_amb = pe_L0_amb * (1 - np.exp(-k * phenology["LAI_mix_L0"])) / 10 #
↳cm/d

rsoil_L0_eco2 = pe_L0_eco2 * np.exp(-k * phenology["LAI_mix_L0"]) / 10 # cm/d
rroot_L0_eco2 = pe_L0_eco2 * (1 - np.exp(-k * phenology["LAI_mix_L0"])) / 10 #
↳cm/d
```

```
[24]: # include Errors
noerror_L0 = periods[(periods["L0_error"] == 0) & (periods["veg_period"] ==
↳1)]["2017":"2020"].index
noerror_L2 = periods[(periods["L2_error"] == 0) & (periods["veg_period"] ==
↳1)]["2017":"2020"].index
```

```
[25]: # hcritA
M = 0.018015 # (kg/mol)
g = 9.81 # m/s2
R = 8.314 # J/mol/K
Hr = meteo["RHmean_%"].copy() / 10 # [-] air humidity
T = meteo["Tmean_C"] + 273.12 # temperature [K]
hcrita_meter = -R * T / M / g * np.log(Hr) # equation 2.74 hydrus manual in
↳meters
hcrita_cm = hcrita_meter * 100
```

5 4 Construct the Hdrus 1D model - 2 layers

```
[26]: def get_idx_from_depth(d, profile):
    return profile.iloc[(profile["x"] - d).abs().argsort()[0:1]].index.
↳to_list()[0]
def roots(depth, r1=5, r2=45):
    sp = 1 - (-depth - r1) / r2
    beta = np.ones(len(depth)) * sp
    beta[depth > -r1] = 1
    beta[depth < -(r2 + r1)] = 0
    return beta
```

```
[27]: hparam = [0.57, 0, 5, 1.5673e016, 2.5347e016, 9.8939e016, 1.4333e014, 1.
↳8737e014, 3.1204e014,]
# icampbelll
heat_params = [hparam, hparam,hparam]
```

```
[28]: hydrus_exe = "hydrus_co2.exe"

def h_1layer(name, prec, rroot, rsoil, soil_params, s1,e1, r2=10):
    exe = os.path.join(os.getcwd(), hydrus_exe)
    # Basic model information
    m1 = ps.Model(
        exe_name=exe,
        ws_name=name,
        name="model",
        mass_units="mmol",
        time_unit="days",
        length_unit="cm", print_screen=False
    )
    m1.basic_info["lSnow"] = True
    m1.basic_info["lTemp"] = True
    # Add time information
    m1.add_time_info(tinit=0, tmax=len(prec), dtmin=1e-4, print_times=True)
    # top_bc=2, Atmospheric Boundary Condition with Surface Layer.
    # top_bc=3, Atmospheric Boundary Condition with Surface Run Off.
```

```

# bot_bc=4, Free Drainage.
# bot_bc=2, Variable Pressure Head
# Define water flow boundary conditions and SHP properties
ml.add_waterflow(top_bc=2, bot_bc=4)
m = ml.get_empty_material_df(n=3)
m.loc[[1,2,3]] = soil_params
ml.add_material(m)

h = ml.get_empty_heat_df()
h.loc[[1,2,3]] = heat_params
# add Heat transport
ml.add_heat_transport(h, ampl=0, top_bc=1, bot_bc=0, top_temp=10,
↳bot_temp=10, icampbell=0)
# add profile
nodes = 140 # Discretize soil column into n elements
depth = [-25, -90, -140] # [-30, -100, -140] # Depth of the soil column
profile = ps.create_profile(bot=depth, dx=abs(depth[-1] / nodes), mat=1)
d1, d2 = get_idx_from_depth(depth[0], profile),
↳get_idx_from_depth(depth[1], profile)
profile.loc[d1:d2, "Mat"] = 2
profile.loc[d2:141, "Mat"] = 3
profile["Beta"] = roots(profile["x"], 10, r2)
profile["Temp"] = np.linspace(stemp.loc["2017-1-1", "temp_5cm_L2"], stemp.
↳loc["2017-1-1", "temp_140cm_L2"], 141)
profile["h"] = np.linspace(-25, -15, 141) # Determine initial Pressure Head
ml.add_profile(profile) # Add the profile
# Add atmospheric boundary conditions
bc = {
    "tAtm": np.arange(len(prec.loc[s1:e1])) + 1,
    "Prec": np.asarray(prec.loc[s1:e1]),
    "tTop": np.asarray(meteo.loc[s1:e1, "Tmean_ [C]"]),
    "tBot": np.asarray(stemp.loc[s1:e1, "temp_140cm_L2"]),
    "rSoil": np.asarray(rsoil.loc[s1:e1]),
    "rRoot": np.asarray(rroot.loc[s1:e1]),
    "hCritA": np.asarray(hcrita_cm.loc[s1:e1]),
} #
atm = pd.DataFrame(bc, index=np.arange(len(prec.loc[s1:e1])))
# add Atmospheric boundary conditions
ml.add_atmospheric_bc(atm, hcrits=0) # , hcrits=-10e8)
# add observation nodes
ml.add_obs_nodes([-10, -30, -140])
# add root water uptake
ml.add_root_uptake(model=1, poptm=[-25, -25, -25], p50=-400)# p2h=-10e5,
↳p2l=-10e5, p3=-10e6)# p2h=-1500, p2l=-1500,)# p50=-80000)p50=-4000)#
ml.write_input() # Write input
ml.simulate()
return ml

```

```
[29]: # lysimeter
s1, e1 = ("2017-1-1", "2020-12-31")
seep_L2_lysi = seep_L2_lysi[s1:e1]
seep_L0_lysi = seep_L0_lysi[s1:e1]
swc10_L2_lysi = sensors["SWC_10_L2"]
swc30_L2_lysi = sensors["SWC_30_L2"]
swc30_L0_lysi = sensors["SWC_30_L0"]
```

```
[30]: # Get results for the soil hydraulic parameters from the inverse estimation
results_L2 = spotpy.analyser.load_csv_results("dream_L2")
# best performing
bestindex, bestobjf = spotpy.analyser.get_maxlikeindex(results_L2)
params_out = list(results_L2[bestindex])[0]
```

Run number 8379 has the highest objectivefunction with: 1796.6616

```
[31]: soil_par_L2 = [[0.05, 0.48, params_out[1], params_out[2], params_out[3], 0.5,],
                    [0.05, 0.395, params_out[4], params_out[5], params_out[6], 0.5,],
                    [0.05, 0.35, params_out[7], params_out[8], params_out[6], 0.5,]]
```

```
[32]: # Run Hydrus-1D
s1,e1=("2016", "2020")
m1_L2_eco2 = h_1layer("L2_eco2", prec_L2, rroot_L2_sim, rsoil_L2_amb,
↳soil_par_L2, s1, e1)
m1_L2_aco2 = h_1layer("L2_aco2", prec_L2, rroot_L2_amb, rsoil_L2_amb,
↳soil_par_L2, s1, e1,)
```

```
[33]: # extract cumulative outflow, averaged SWC, matric head at 30 cm
rroot_L2_eco2_sim1 = pd.Series(((m1_L2_eco2.read_alevel()["sum(rRoot)"]).
↳diff()[366:] * 10).values, index=prec_L2["2017":"2020"].index)
rroot_L2_aco2_sim1 = pd.Series(((m1_L2_aco2.read_alevel()["sum(rRoot)"]).
↳diff()[366:] * 10).values, index=prec_L2["2017":"2020"].index)

vroot_L2_eco2_sim1 = pd.Series(((m1_L2_eco2.read_alevel()["sum(vRoot)"]).
↳diff()[366:] * 10).values, index=prec_L2["2017":"2020"].index)
vroot_L2_aco2_sim1 = pd.Series(((m1_L2_aco2.read_alevel()["sum(vRoot)"]).
↳diff()[366:] * 10).values, index=prec_L2["2017":"2020"].index)

seep_L2_eco2_sim1 = pd.Series(((m1_L2_eco2.read_alevel()["sum(vBot)"] * -1).
↳diff()[366:]).values, index=prec_L2["2017":"2020"].index)
seep_L2_aco2_sim1 = pd.Series(((m1_L2_aco2.read_alevel()["sum(vBot)"] * -1).
↳diff()[366:]).values, index=prec_L2["2017":"2020"].index)

swc30_L2_eco2_sim1 = pd.Series((m1_L2_eco2.read_obs_node()[31]["theta"][367:] *
↳100).values, index=prec_L2["2017":"2020"].index)
swc30_L2_aco2_sim1 = pd.Series((m1_L2_aco2.read_obs_node()[31]["theta"][367:] *
↳100).values, index=prec_L2["2017":"2020"].index)
```

```

swc10_L2_eco2_sim1 = pd.Series((ml_L2_eco2.read_obs_node()[11]["theta"][367:] *
↳100).values, index=prec_L2["2017":"2020"].index)
swc10_L2_aco2_sim1 = pd.Series((ml_L2_aco2.read_obs_node()[11]["theta"][367:] *
↳100).values, index=prec_L2["2017":"2020"].index)

```

```

[34]: s1,e1=("2018","2020")
print((rroot_L2_lysi[s1:e1] * 10).sum())
print(vroot_L2_eco2_sim1[s1:e1].sum())
print(vroot_L2_aco2_sim1[s1:e1].sum())
print((seep_L2_lysi[s1:e1]).sum())
print(seep_L2_eco2_sim1[s1:e1].sum())
print(seep_L2_aco2_sim1[s1:e1].sum())

```

```

1172.1321803754936
1176.539
1221.255
146.39700000000002
144.893
140.73700000000002

```

```

[35]: idx_veg = periods[periods["veg_period"]==1].loc["2018":"2020"].index
idx_veg18 = periods[periods["veg_period"]==1].loc["2018"].index
idx_veg19 = periods[periods["veg_period"]==1].loc["2019"].index
idx_veg20 = periods[periods["veg_period"]==1].loc["2020"].index
idx_veg18s = periods[periods["veg_period"]==1].loc["2018"].index.union(pd.
↳date_range("2018-9-1","2018-12-31"))
idx_veg19s = periods[periods["veg_period"]==1].loc["2019"].index.union(pd.
↳date_range("2019-9-1","2019-12-31"))
idx_veg20s = periods[periods["veg_period"]==1].loc["2020"].index.union(pd.
↳date_range("2020-9-1","2020-12-31"))
idx_vegs = idx_veg18s.union(idx_veg19s).union(idx_veg20s)

```

```

[36]: # We overestimate potential transpiration, actual transpiration and
↳underestimate seepage by:
print((rroot_L2_aco2_sim1[idx_veg18].sum()-rroot_L2_eco2_sim1[idx_veg18].sum())/
↳rroot_L2_eco2_sim1[idx_veg18].sum()*100)
print((rroot_L2_aco2_sim1[idx_veg19].sum()-rroot_L2_eco2_sim1[idx_veg19].sum())/
↳rroot_L2_eco2_sim1[idx_veg19].sum()*100)
print((rroot_L2_aco2_sim1[idx_veg20].sum()-rroot_L2_eco2_sim1[idx_veg20].sum())/
↳rroot_L2_eco2_sim1[idx_veg20].sum()*100)
print((vroot_L2_aco2_sim1[idx_veg18].sum()-vroot_L2_eco2_sim1[idx_veg18].sum())/
↳vroot_L2_eco2_sim1[idx_veg18].sum()*100)
print((vroot_L2_aco2_sim1[idx_veg19].sum()-vroot_L2_eco2_sim1[idx_veg19].sum())/
↳vroot_L2_eco2_sim1[idx_veg19].sum()*100)
print((vroot_L2_aco2_sim1[idx_veg20].sum()-vroot_L2_eco2_sim1[idx_veg20].sum())/
↳vroot_L2_eco2_sim1[idx_veg20].sum()*100)

```

```

print((seep_L2_aco2_sim1[idx_veg18s].sum()-seep_L2_eco2_sim1[idx_veg18s].sum())/
↪seep_L2_eco2_sim1[idx_veg18s].sum()*100)
print((seep_L2_aco2_sim1[idx_veg19s].sum()-seep_L2_eco2_sim1[idx_veg19s].sum())/
↪seep_L2_eco2_sim1[idx_veg19s].sum()*100)
print((seep_L2_aco2_sim1[idx_veg20s].sum()-seep_L2_eco2_sim1[idx_veg20s].sum())/
↪seep_L2_eco2_sim1[idx_veg20s].sum()*100)

```

```

5.250060737291776
5.7774024123097005
6.4779563486297596
2.3958631687322054
3.6796233500545332
6.4779563486297596
-4.568810747229617
-4.203713389121345
-6.78965143694632

```

```

[37]: s1,e1=("2018-1-1","2020-12-31")
axslabels = 7
xylabels = 6
legends = 6
texts = 6

cm = 1 / 2.54 # centimeters in inches
mosaic=""
AB
CD
""

fig,axs = plt.subplot_mosaic(mosaic, sharex=True, figsize=(figw_2c*cm, 7*cm),
↪dpi=300)
for word in ("B", "D"):
    axs[word].yaxis.tick_right()
    axs[word].yaxis.set_label_position("right")
#A

l1, = axs["A"].plot(rroot_L2_eco2_sim1[s1:e1].cumsum(), linewidth=1,
↪linestyle="--",
    label=r"Sim potential T at $eCO_2$", color="#1f77b4",)
l2, = axs["A"].plot(rroot_L2_aco2_sim1[s1:e1].cumsum(), linewidth=1,
↪linestyle="--",
    label=r"Sim potential T at $aCO_2$", color="darkorange",)
leg1 = axs["A"].legend([l1,l2],[r"Sim potential T at $eCO_2$",r"Sim potential T
↪at $aCO_2$"], loc='lower right', frameon=False, fontsize=legends)

l3, = axs["A"].plot((rroot_L2_lysi[s1:e1] * 10).cumsum(), "ko",
    linewidth=0.1, markersize=1, label=r"Transpiration (T) from Lysimeter
↪ET",)

```

```

14, = axs["A"].plot(vroot_L2_eco2_sim1[s1:e1].cumsum(), linewidth=1,
    label=r"Sim. actual T at $eCO_2$", color="#1f77b4",)
15, = axs["A"].plot(vroot_L2_aco2_sim1[s1:e1].cumsum(), linewidth=1,
    ↪linestyle="--",
    label=r"Sim. actual T at $aCO_2$", color="darkorange",)
axs["A"].set_ylabel("Transpiration [mm.d$^{-1}$]", size=axslabels)
leg2 = axs["A"].legend([13,14,15],[r"Transpiration (T) from Lysimeter ET",
    ↪r"Sim. actual T at $eCO_2$", r"Sim. actual T at $aCO_2$"],
    frameon=False, fontsize=legends, loc="upper left")
axs["A"].add_artist(leg1)

# B
axs["B"].plot(seep_L2_lysi[s1:e1].cumsum(), "ko", linewidth=0.1,
    markersize=1, label=r"Cumulative L2 seepage",)
    # axs[2, 1].plot(seep_L0_lysi[s1:e1].cumsum(), "kx", linewidth=0.1,
    #     markersize=1, label=r"Cumulative L0 seepage",)
axs["B"].plot(seep_L2_eco2_sim1[s1:e1].cumsum(), linewidth=1,
    label=r"Sim. seepage with $PETc_{+300ppm-CO_2}$", color="#1f77b4",)
axs["B"].plot(seep_L2_aco2_sim1[s1:e1].cumsum(), linewidth=1, linestyle="--",
    label=r"Sim. seepage with $PETc_{ambient}$", color="darkorange",)
axs["B"].set_ylabel(r"Cum. seepage [mm.d$^{-1}$]", size=axslabels)
axs["B"].legend(frameon=False, fontsize=legends, loc="upper left")

# C
axs["C"].plot(swc30_L2_lysi[s1:e1], "ko", linewidth=0.1, markersize=1,
    ↪label=r"SWC-30 - Lysimeter")
axs["C"].plot(swc30_L2_eco2_sim1[s1:e1], linewidth=1,
    label=r"SWC-30 - $PETc_{+300ppm-CO_2}$", color="#1f77b4",)
axs["C"].plot(swc30_L2_aco2_sim1[s1:e1], linewidth=1, linestyle="--",
    label=r"SWC-30 - $PETc_{ambient}$", color="darkorange",);
axs["C"].set_ylabel("SWC [%]", size=axslabels)
axs["C"].legend(frameon=False, fontsize=legends, loc="lower left")

# D
axs["D"].plot(seep_L2_lysi[s1:e1], "ko", linewidth=0.1, markersize=1,
    ↪label=r"Seep. at lysimeter")
    #axs[1, 1].plot(seep_L0_lysi[s1:e1], color="darkorange", marker="x",
    ↪linewidth=0.1, markersize=1, label=r"Lysimeter L0 seepage")
axs["D"].plot(seep_L2_eco2_sim1[s1:e1], linewidth=1,
    label=r"Seep. $PETc_{eCO_2}$", color="#1f77b4",)
axs["D"].plot(seep_L2_aco2_sim1[s1:e1], linewidth=0.7, linestyle="--",
    label=r"Seep. $PETc_{amb.}$", color="darkorange",)
axs["D"].set_ylabel("Seep. [mm.d$^{-1}$]", size=axslabels)
axs["D"].legend(frameon=False, fontsize=legends, loc="upper left", ncol=3)

# Set lims and ticks
for key in axs.keys():

```

```

    axs[key].set_xlim(pd.Timestamp(s1), pd.Timestamp(e1))
    axs[key].set_xticks([pd.Timestamp("2018-1-1"), pd.Timestamp("2018-7-1"), pd.
↳Timestamp("2019-1-1"),
                        pd.Timestamp("2019-7-1"), pd.Timestamp("2020-1-1"), pd.
↳Timestamp("2020-7-1"), pd.Timestamp("2020-12-31")],)
    axs[key].set_xticklabels(["Jan-18", "Jul-18", "Jan-19", "Jul-19", "Jan-20",
↳"Jul-20", ""])

axs["A"].set_ylim(0,1400)
axs["B"].set_ylim(0,160)
axs["D"].set_ylim(0, 4)
axs["C"].set_ylim(20, 45)
axs["C"].set_yticks([20,25,30,35,40,]);

# inset_axes for seepage 1
axins = axs["D"].inset_axes([0.1, 0.4, 0.15, 0.33])
s1, e1 = ("2018-10-27", "2018-11-17")
axins.plot(seep_L2_lysi[s1:e1], "ko", linewidth=0.1, markersize=1,
↳label=r"Lysimeter L2 Seep")
    #axins.plot(seep_L0_lysi[s1:e1], "kx", linewidth=0.1, markersize=1,
↳label=r"Lysimeter L0 Seep")
axins.plot(seep_L2_eco2_sim1[s1:e1], linewidth=0.7, label=r"Seep. with
↳$ETc_{+300ppm-CO_2}$", color="#1f77b4",)
axins.plot(seep_L2_aco2_sim1[s1:e1], linewidth=0.7, linestyle="--",
↳label=r"Seep. with $ETc_{amb}$", color="darkorange",)
axins.set_xticks(["2018-10-27", "2018-11-17"])
axins.set_xticklabels(("27.oct", "17.nov"))
axins.tick_params(axis="both", direction="in", labelsize=texts)
axins.set_xlim(pd.Timestamp("2018-10-27"), pd.Timestamp("2018-11-17"))
axins.set_ylim(0, 1)
rect = mpatches.Rectangle((pd.Timestamp("2018-10-17"), -0.14),
pd.Timedelta(34, "D"), 1.14, linewidth=0.4, edgecolor="black",
↳facecolor="none", zorder=10,)
axs["D"].add_patch(rect)

# inset_axes for seepage 1
axins = axs["D"].inset_axes([0.44, 0.4, 0.15, 0.33])
s1, e1 = ("2019-10-9", "2019-10-27")
axins.plot(seep_L2_lysi[s1:e1], "ko", linewidth=0.1, markersize=1,
↳label=r"Lysimeter L2 Seep")
axins.plot(seep_L2_eco2_sim1[s1:e1], linewidth=0.7, label=r"Seep. with
↳$ETc_{+300ppm-CO_2}$", color="#1f77b4",)
axins.plot(seep_L2_aco2_sim1[s1:e1], linewidth=0.7, linestyle="--",
↳label=r"Seep. with $ETc_{amb}$", color="darkorange",)
axins.set_xticks(["2019-10-09", "2019-10-27"])
axins.set_xticklabels(("9.oct", "27.oct"))

```

```

axins.tick_params(axis="both", direction="in", labels=texts)
axins.set_xlim(pd.Timestamp("2019-10-09"), pd.Timestamp("2019-10-27"))
axins.set_ylim(0, 0.5)
rect = mpatches.Rectangle((pd.Timestamp("2019-10-05"), -0.14),
pd.Timedelta(21, "D"), 0.64, linewidth=0.4, edgecolor="black",
↳facecolor="none", zorder=10,)
axs["D"].add_patch(rect)

# inset_axes for seepage 2
axins = axs["D"].inset_axes([0.78, 0.4, 0.15, 0.33])
s1, e1 = ("2020-07-01", "2020-07-17")
axins.plot(seep_L2_lysi[s1:e1], "ko", linewidth=0.1, markersize=1,
↳label=r"Lysimeter L2 Seep")
    #axins.plot(seep_L0_lysi[s1:e1], "kx", linewidth=0.1, markersize=1,
↳label=r"Lysimeter L0 Seep")
axins.plot(seep_L2_eco2_sim1[s1:e1], linewidth=0.7, label=r"Seep. with
↳$ETc_{+300ppm-CO_2}$", color="#1f77b4",)
axins.plot(seep_L2_aco2_sim1[s1:e1], linewidth=0.7, linestyle="--",
↳label=r"Seep. with $ETc_{amb}$", color="darkorange",)
axins.set_xticks([s1,e1])
axins.set_xticklabels(("1.jul", "17.jul"))
axins.tick_params(axis="both", direction="in", labels=texts)
axins.set_xlim(pd.Timestamp(s1), pd.Timestamp(e1))
axins.set_ylim(0, 0.5)
rect = mpatches.Rectangle((pd.Timestamp("2020-6-27"), -0.14),
pd.Timedelta(21, "D"), 0.64, linewidth=0.4, edgecolor="black",
↳facecolor="none", zorder=10,)
axs["D"].add_patch(rect)

plt.subplots_adjust(hspace=0, wspace=0, right=0.95, left=0.06, top=0.97,
↳bottom=0.04)
#fig.savefig("figures/figure8.png", dpi=300)

```



```
[38]: # best performing
results_L0 = spotpy.analyser.load_csv_results("dream_L0")
bestindex, bestobjf = spotpy.analyser.get_maxlikeindex(results_L0)
params_out = list(results_L0[bestindex])[0]
soil_par_L0 = [[0.05, 0.48, params_out[1], params_out[2], params_out[3], 0.5,],
               [0.05, 0.395, params_out[4], params_out[5], params_out[6], 0.5,],
               [0.05, 0.35, params_out[7], params_out[8], params_out[6], 0.5,]]
soil_par_L0
```

Run number 13181 has the highest objectivefunction with: 1440.5011

```
[38]: [[0.05, 0.48, 0.010433292, 1.193328, 30.145884, 0.5],
       [0.05, 0.395, 0.010071014, 1.2498581, 75.987305, 0.5],
       [0.05, 0.35, 0.07971647, 1.210685, 75.987305, 0.5]]
```

```
[39]: s1,e1=("2016", "2020")
ml_L0_aco2 = h_1layer("L0_aco2", prec_L0, rroot_L0_amb, rsoil_L0_amb,
                    ↪soil_par_L0, s1, e1,)
ml_L0_eco2 = h_1layer("L0_eco2", prec_L0, rroot_L0_eco2, rsoil_L0_amb,
                    ↪soil_par_L0, s1, e1,)
```

6 Show uncertainty

```
[40]: # sample 20 random from results
soil_L2 = results_L2[-50:].copy()
soil_L0 = results_L0[-50:].copy()
```

```
[41]: rroot_L2_eco2_sim = []
rroot_L2_amb_sim = []
rroot_L0_amb_sim = []
rroot_L0_eco2_sim = []

vroot_L2_eco2_sim = []
vroot_L2_amb_sim = []
vroot_L0_amb_sim = []
vroot_L0_eco2_sim = []

seep_L2_eco2_sim = []
seep_L2_amb_sim = []
seep_L0_amb_sim = []
seep_L0_eco2_sim = []

swc_L2_eco2_sim = []
swc_L2_amb_sim = []
```

```

swc_L0_amb_sim = []
swc_L0_eco2_sim = []

for s12, s10 in zip(soil_L2, soil_L0):
    s1, e1 = ("2016", "2020-12-31")
    soil_par_L2 = [[0.05, 0.48, s12[1], s12[2], s12[3], 0.5,],
                  [0.05, 0.395, s12[4], s12[5], s12[6], 0.5,],
                  [0.05, 0.35, s12[7], s12[8], s12[6], 0.5,]]
    soil_par_L0 = [[0.05, 0.48, s10[1], s10[2], s10[3], 0.5,],
                  [0.05, 0.395, s10[4], s10[5], s10[6], 0.5,],
                  [0.05, 0.35, s10[7], s10[8], s10[6], 0.5,]]

    ml_L2_eco2 = h_1layer("L2_eco2", prec_L2, rroot_L2_sim, rsoil_L2_amb,
↳soil_par_L2, s1, e1,)
    ml_L2_aco2 = h_1layer("L2_aco2", prec_L2, rroot_L2_amb, rsoil_L2_amb,
↳soil_par_L2, s1, e1,)
    ml_L0_aco2 = h_1layer("L0_aco2", prec_L0, rroot_L0_amb, rsoil_L0_amb,
↳soil_par_L0, s1, e1,)
    ml_L0_eco2 = h_1layer("L0_eco2", prec_L0, rroot_L0_eco2, rsoil_L0_amb,
↳soil_par_L0, s1, e1,)
    # extract cumulative outflow, averaged SWC, matric head at 30 cm
    rroot_L2_eco2_sim.append(((ml_L2_eco2.read_alevel()["sum(rRoot)"]).
↳diff()[366:] * 10).values)
    rroot_L2_amb_sim.append(((ml_L2_aco2.read_alevel()["sum(rRoot)"]).
↳diff()[366:] * 10).values)
    rroot_L0_amb_sim.append(((ml_L0_aco2.read_alevel()["sum(rRoot)"]).
↳diff()[366:] * 10).values)
    rroot_L0_eco2_sim.append(((ml_L0_eco2.read_alevel()["sum(rRoot)"]).
↳diff()[366:] * 10).values)

    vroot_L2_eco2_sim.append(((ml_L2_eco2.read_alevel()["sum(vRoot)"]).
↳diff()[366:] * 10).values)
    vroot_L2_amb_sim.append(((ml_L2_aco2.read_alevel()["sum(vRoot)"]).
↳diff()[366:] * 10).values)
    vroot_L0_amb_sim.append(((ml_L0_aco2.read_alevel()["sum(vRoot)"]).
↳diff()[366:] * 10).values)
    vroot_L0_eco2_sim.append(((ml_L0_eco2.read_alevel()["sum(vRoot)"]).
↳diff()[366:] * 10).values)

    seep_L2_eco2_sim.append(((ml_L2_eco2.read_alevel()["sum(vBot)"] * -1).
↳diff()[366:]).values)
    seep_L2_amb_sim.append(((ml_L2_aco2.read_alevel()["sum(vBot)"] * -1).
↳diff()[366:]).values)
    seep_L0_amb_sim.append(((ml_L0_aco2.read_alevel()["sum(vBot)"] * -1).
↳diff()[366:]).values)

```

```

seep_L0_eco2_sim.append(((ml_L0_eco2.read_alevel()["sum(vBot)"] * -1).
↳diff()[366:]).values)

swc_L2_eco2_sim.append((ml_L2_eco2.read_obs_node()[31]["theta"][367:] *
↳100).values)
swc_L2_amb_sim.append((ml_L2_aco2.read_obs_node()[31]["theta"][367:] * 100).
↳values)
swc_L0_amb_sim.append((ml_L0_aco2.read_obs_node()[31]["theta"][367:] * 100).
↳values)
swc_L0_eco2_sim.append((ml_L0_eco2.read_obs_node()[31]["theta"][367:] *
↳100).values)

```

```

[42]: # daily
swc_L2amb_5, swc_L2eco2_5, swc_L2amb_95, swc_L2eco2_95, swc_L2amb_50,
↳swc_L2eco2_50 = [], [], [], [], [], []
s_L2amb_5, s_L2eco2_5, s_L2amb_95, s_L2eco2_95, s_L2amb_50, s_L2eco2_50 =
↳[], [], [], [], [], []
t_L2amb_5, t_L2eco2_5, t_L2amb_95, t_L2eco2_95, t_L2amb_50, t_L2eco2_50 =
↳[], [], [], [], [], []
swc_L0amb_5, swc_L0eco2_5, swc_L0amb_95, swc_L0eco2_95, swc_L0amb_50,
↳swc_L0eco2_50 = [], [], [], [], [], []
s_L0amb_5, s_L0eco2_5, s_L0amb_95, s_L0eco2_95, s_L0amb_50, s_L0eco2_50 =
↳[], [], [], [], [], []
t_L0amb_5, t_L0eco2_5, t_L0amb_95, t_L0eco2_95, t_L0amb_50, t_L0eco2_50 =
↳[], [], [], [], [], []

for i in np.arange(0, len(rroot_L2_eco2_sim[0])):
swc_L2amb_5.append(np.percentile(np.array(swc_L2_amb_sim)[: , i], 2.5))
swc_L2eco2_5.append(np.percentile(np.array(swc_L2_eco2_sim)[: , i], 2.5))
swc_L2amb_95.append(np.percentile(np.array(swc_L2_amb_sim)[: , i], 97.5))
swc_L2eco2_95.append(np.percentile(np.array(swc_L2_eco2_sim)[: , i], 97.5))
swc_L2amb_50.append(np.percentile(np.array(swc_L2_amb_sim)[: , i], 50))
swc_L2eco2_50.append(np.percentile(np.array(swc_L2_eco2_sim)[: , i], 50))
s_L2amb_5.append(np.percentile(np.array(seep_L2_amb_sim)[: , i], 2.5))
s_L2eco2_5.append(np.percentile(np.array(seep_L2_eco2_sim)[: , i], 2.5))
s_L2amb_95.append(np.percentile(np.array(seep_L2_amb_sim)[: , i], 97.5))
s_L2eco2_95.append(np.percentile(np.array(seep_L2_eco2_sim)[: , i], 97.5))
s_L2amb_50.append(np.percentile(np.array(seep_L2_amb_sim)[: , i], 50))
s_L2eco2_50.append(np.percentile(np.array(seep_L2_eco2_sim)[: , i], 50))
t_L2amb_5.append(np.percentile(np.array(vroot_L2_amb_sim)[: , i], 2.5))
t_L2eco2_5.append(np.percentile(np.array(vroot_L2_eco2_sim)[: , i], 2.5))
t_L2amb_95.append(np.percentile(np.array(vroot_L2_amb_sim)[: , i], 97.5))
t_L2eco2_95.append(np.percentile(np.array(vroot_L2_eco2_sim)[: , i], 97.5))
t_L2amb_50.append(np.percentile(np.array(vroot_L2_amb_sim)[: , i], 50))
t_L2eco2_50.append(np.percentile(np.array(vroot_L2_eco2_sim)[: , i], 50))
swc_L0amb_5.append(np.percentile(np.array(swc_L0_amb_sim)[: , i], 2.5))

```

```

swc_L0eco2_5.append(np.percentile(np.array(swc_L0_eco2_sim)[: ,i],2.5))
swc_L0amb_95.append(np.percentile(np.array(swc_L0_amb_sim)[: ,i],97.5))
swc_L0eco2_95.append(np.percentile(np.array(swc_L0_eco2_sim)[: ,i],97.5))
swc_L0amb_50.append(np.percentile(np.array(swc_L0_amb_sim)[: ,i],50))
swc_L0eco2_50.append(np.percentile(np.array(swc_L0_eco2_sim)[: ,i],50))
s_L0amb_5.append(np.percentile(np.array(seep_L0_amb_sim)[: ,i],2.5))
s_L0eco2_5.append(np.percentile(np.array(seep_L0_eco2_sim)[: ,i],2.5))
s_L0amb_95.append(np.percentile(np.array(seep_L0_amb_sim)[: ,i],97.5))
s_L0eco2_95.append(np.percentile(np.array(seep_L0_eco2_sim)[: ,i],97.5))
s_L0amb_50.append(np.percentile(np.array(seep_L0_amb_sim)[: ,i],50))
s_L0eco2_50.append(np.percentile(np.array(seep_L0_eco2_sim)[: ,i],50))
t_L0amb_5.append(np.percentile(np.array(vroot_L0_amb_sim)[: ,i],2.5))
t_L0eco2_5.append(np.percentile(np.array(vroot_L0_eco2_sim)[: ,i],2.5))
t_L0amb_95.append(np.percentile(np.array(vroot_L0_amb_sim)[: ,i],97.5))
t_L0eco2_95.append(np.percentile(np.array(vroot_L0_eco2_sim)[: ,i],97.5))
t_L0amb_50.append(np.percentile(np.array(vroot_L0_amb_sim)[: ,i],50))
t_L0eco2_50.append(np.percentile(np.array(vroot_L0_eco2_sim)[: ,i],50))

```

```

[43]: fluxes_sim = pd.DataFrame({"swc_L2amb_5":swc_L2amb_5, "swc_L2eco2_5":
↳swc_L2eco2_5,
                                     "swc_L2amb_95":swc_L2amb_95, "swc_L2eco2_95":
↳swc_L2eco2_95,
                                     "swc_L2amb_50":swc_L2amb_50, "swc_L2eco2_50":
↳swc_L2eco2_50,
                                     "s_L2amb_5":s_L2amb_5, "s_L2eco2_5":s_L2eco2_5,
                                     "s_L2amb_50":s_L2amb_50, "s_L2eco2_50":s_L2eco2_50,
                                     "s_L2amb_95":s_L2amb_95, "s_L2eco2_95":s_L2eco2_95,
                                     "t_L2amb_5":t_L2amb_5, "t_L2eco2_5":t_L2eco2_5,
                                     "t_L2amb_50":t_L2amb_50, "t_L2eco2_50":t_L2eco2_50,
                                     "t_L2amb_95":t_L2amb_95, "t_L2eco2_95":t_L2eco2_95,
                                     "swc_L0amb_5":swc_L0amb_5, "swc_L0eco2_5":
↳swc_L0eco2_5,
                                     "swc_L0amb_95":swc_L0amb_95, "swc_L0eco2_95":
↳swc_L0eco2_95,
                                     "swc_L0amb_50":swc_L0amb_50, "swc_L0eco2_50":
↳swc_L0eco2_50,
                                     "s_L0amb_5":s_L0amb_5, "s_L0eco2_5":s_L0eco2_5,
                                     "s_L0amb_50":s_L0amb_50, "s_L0eco2_50":s_L0eco2_50,
                                     "s_L0amb_95":s_L0amb_95, "s_L0eco2_95":s_L0eco2_95,
                                     "t_L0amb_5":t_L0amb_5, "t_L0eco2_5":t_L0eco2_5,
                                     "t_L0amb_50":t_L0amb_50, "t_L0eco2_50":t_L0eco2_50,
                                     "t_L0amb_95":t_L0amb_95, "t_L0eco2_95":t_L0eco2_95},
↳index=prec_L2["2017":"2020"].index)

```

```

[44]: vroot_L2_all = pd.DataFrame(np.array(vroot_L2_eco2_sim).T, index=prec_L2["2017":
↳"2020"].index)

```

```

seep_L2_all = pd.DataFrame(np.array(seep_L2_eco2_sim).T, index=prec_L2["2017":
↳"2020"].index)
vroot_L0_all = pd.DataFrame(np.array(vroot_L0_amb_sim).T, index=prec_L2["2017":
↳"2020"].index)
seep_L0_all = pd.DataFrame(np.array(seep_L0_amb_sim).T, index=prec_L2["2017":
↳"2020"].index)

```

```

[45]: idx_veg = periods[periods["veg_period"]==1].loc["2018":"2020"].index
idx_veg18 = periods[periods["veg_period"]==1].loc["2018"].index
idx_veg19 = periods[periods["veg_period"]==1].loc["2019"].index
idx_veg20 = periods[periods["veg_period"]==1].loc["2020"].index
idx_veg18s = periods[periods["veg_period"]==1].loc["2018"].index.union(pd.
↳date_range("2018-9-1", "2018-12-31"))
idx_veg19s = periods[periods["veg_period"]==1].loc["2019"].index.union(pd.
↳date_range("2019-9-1", "2019-12-31"))
idx_veg20s = periods[periods["veg_period"]==1].loc["2020"].index.union(pd.
↳date_range("2020-9-1", "2020-12-31"))
idx_vegs = idx_veg18s.union(idx_veg19s).union(idx_veg20s)

```

```

[46]: # Print KGE
print("-", "-", kge((rroot_L0_lysi.loc[idx_veg]*10), fluxes_sim.
↳loc[idx_veg, "t_L0amb_50"]).round(2),
      kge(seep_L0_lysi.loc[idx_vegs], fluxes_sim.loc[idx_vegs, "s_L0amb_50"])).
↳round(2))
print("-", "-", kge((rroot_L2_lysi.loc[idx_veg]*10), fluxes_sim.
↳loc[idx_veg, "t_L2eco2_50"]).round(2),
      kge(seep_L2_lysi.loc[idx_vegs], fluxes_sim.loc[idx_vegs, "s_L2eco2_50"])).
↳round(2))
for year in ("2018", "2019", "2020"):
    idx_vegt = periods[periods["veg_period"]==1].loc[year].index
    idx_vegs = periods[periods["veg_period"]==1].loc[year].index.union(pd.
↳date_range(year+"-9-1", year+"-12-31"))
    print((rroot_L0_lysi.loc[idx_vegt]*10).sum().round(1), seep_L0_lysi.
↳loc[idx_vegs].sum().round(1),
          fluxes_sim.loc[idx_vegt, "t_L0amb_50"].sum().round(1),
          "{+--{}}%".format(np.round((vroot_L0_all.loc[idx_vegt, :].sum().std()/
↳vroot_L0_all.loc[idx_vegt, :].sum().quantile(0.5)*100), 1)),
          fluxes_sim.loc[idx_vegs, "s_L0amb_50"].sum().round(1),
          "{+--{}}%".format(np.round((seep_L0_all.loc[idx_vegs, :].sum().std()/
↳seep_L0_all.loc[idx_vegs, :].sum().quantile(0.5)*100), 1)),)
    print((rroot_L2_lysi.loc[idx_vegt]*10).sum().round(1), seep_L2_lysi.
↳loc[idx_vegs].sum().round(1),
          fluxes_sim.loc[idx_vegt, "t_L2eco2_50"].sum().round(1),
          "{+--{}}%".format(np.round((vroot_L2_all.loc[idx_vegt, :].sum().std()/
↳vroot_L2_all.loc[idx_vegt, :].sum().quantile(0.5)*100), 1)),
          fluxes_sim.loc[idx_vegs, "s_L2eco2_50"].sum().round(1),

```

```
"(+{-}%)".format(np.round((seep_L2_all.loc[idx_vegs,:].sum().std()/
↪seep_L2_all.loc[idx_vegs,:].sum().quantile(0.5)*100),1),)
```

```
- - 0.9 0.87
- - 0.85 0.89
436.3 16.8 410.7 (+-0.3%) 13.3 (+-1.0%)
407.7 15.8 387.8 (+-0.3%) 16.0 (+-1.2%)
348.9 25.3 371.9 (+-0.3%) 26.3 (+-0.3%)
342.2 28.0 357.3 (+-0.3%) 30.5 (+-0.4%)
352.1 28.4 372.3 (+-0.0%) 27.2 (+-0.1%)
334.2 31.8 344.1 (+-0.0%) 31.4 (+-0.1%)
```

```
[47]: # C0mpute SNR
uncert_s_L0 = (seep_L0_all.loc[idx_veg,:].resample("y").sum().std(axis=1)/
↪seep_L0_all.loc[idx_veg,:].resample("y").sum().mean(axis=1)).mean()+1
snr_num_s_L0 = abs(((fluxes_sim.loc[idx_vegs,"s_L0amb_50"].resample("y").
↪sum()-fluxes_sim.loc[idx_vegs,"s_L0eco2_50"].resample("y").sum())/fluxes_sim.
↪loc[idx_vegs,"s_L0amb_50"].resample("y").sum()).mean())
snr_den_s_L0 = abs(((fluxes_sim.loc[idx_vegs,"s_L0amb_50"].resample("y").
↪sum()-fluxes_sim.loc[idx_vegs,"s_L0amb_50"].resample("y").sum()*uncert_s_L0)/
↪fluxes_sim.loc[idx_vegs,"s_L0amb_50"].resample("y").sum()).mean())
print("SNR_s_L0={}".format(np.round(snr_num_s_L0/snr_den_s_L0-1,1)))

uncert_s_L2 = (seep_L2_all.loc[idx_veg,:].resample("y").sum().std(axis=1)/
↪seep_L2_all.loc[idx_veg,:].resample("y").sum().mean(axis=1)).mean()+1
snr_num_s_L2 = abs(((fluxes_sim.loc[idx_vegs,"s_L2amb_50"].resample("y").
↪sum()-fluxes_sim.loc[idx_vegs,"s_L2eco2_50"].resample("y").sum())/fluxes_sim.
↪loc[idx_vegs,"s_L2amb_50"].resample("y").sum()).mean())
snr_den_s_L2 = abs(((fluxes_sim.loc[idx_vegs,"s_L2amb_50"].resample("y").
↪sum()-fluxes_sim.loc[idx_vegs,"s_L2amb_50"].resample("y").sum()*uncert_s_L2)/
↪fluxes_sim.loc[idx_vegs,"s_L2amb_50"].resample("y").sum()).mean())
print("SNR_s_L2={}".format(np.round(snr_num_s_L2/snr_den_s_L2-1,1)))
```

```
SNR_s_L0=7.4
SNR_s_L2=3.8
```

```
[48]: s1,e1=("2018-1-1","2020-12-31")
axlabels = 7
xlables = 6
legends = 6
texts = 6

cm = 1 / 2.54 # centimeters in inches
mosaic=""
AB
CD
""
```

```

fig,axs = plt.subplot_mosaic(mosaic, sharex=True, figsize=(figw_2c*cm, 7*cm),
    ↪dpi=300)
for word in ("B", "D"):
    axs[word].yaxis.tick_right()
    axs[word].yaxis.set_label_position("right")
#A

l1, = axs["A"].plot(rroot_L2_eco2_sim1[s1:e1].cumsum(), linewidth=1,
    ↪linestyle="--",
    label=r"Sim potential T at $eCO_2$", color="#1f77b4",)
l2, = axs["A"].plot(rroot_L2_aco2_sim1[s1:e1].cumsum(), linewidth=1,
    ↪linestyle="--",
    label=r"Sim potential T at $aCO_2$", color="darkorange",)
leg1 = axs["A"].legend([l1,l2],[r"Sim potential T at $eCO_2$",r"Sim potential T
    ↪at $aCO_2$"],
    loc='upper left', frameon=False, fontsize=legends,
    ↪numpoints=3)

l3, = axs["A"].plot((rroot_L2_lysi[s1:e1] * 10).cumsum(), "ko",
    linewidth=0.1, markersize=1, label=r"Transpiration (T) from Lysimeter
    ↪ET",)
l4, = axs["A"].plot(vroot_L2_eco2_sim1[s1:e1].cumsum(), linewidth=1,
    label=r"Sim. actual T at $eCO_2$", color="#1f77b4",)
l5, = axs["A"].plot(vroot_L2_aco2_sim1[s1:e1].cumsum(), linewidth=1,
    ↪linestyle="-",
    label=r"Sim. actual T at $aCO_2$", color="darkorange",)
axs["A"].set_ylabel("Transpiration [mm.d$^{-1}$]", size=axslabels)
leg2 = axs["A"].legend([l3,l4,l5],[r"Transpiration (T) from Lysimeter ET",
    ↪r"Sim. actual T at $eCO_2$", r"Sim. actual T at $aCO_2$"],
    frameon=False, fontsize=legends, loc="lower right",
    ↪numpoints=3)
axs["A"].add_artist(leg1)

# B
axs["B"].plot(seep_L2_lysi[s1:e1].cumsum(), "ko", linewidth=0.1,
    markersize=1, label=r"Cumulative L2 seepage",)
# axs[2, 1].plot(seep_L0_lysi[s1:e1].cumsum(), "kx", linewidth=0.1,
#     markersize=1, label=r"Cumulative L0 seepage",)
axs["B"].plot(seep_L2_eco2_sim1[s1:e1].cumsum(), linewidth=1,
    label=r"Sim. seepage with $PETc_{+300ppm-CO_2}$", color="#1f77b4",)
axs["B"].plot(seep_L2_aco2_sim1[s1:e1].cumsum(), linewidth=1, linestyle="--",
    label=r"Sim. seepage with $PETc_{ambient}$", color="darkorange",)
axs["B"].set_ylabel(r"Cum. seepage [mm.d$^{-1}$]", size=axslabels)
axs["B"].legend(frameon=False, fontsize=legends, loc="upper left", numpoints=3)

# C

```

```

axs["C"].plot(swc30_L2_lysi[s1:e1], "ko", linewidth=0.1, markersize=1,
↳label=r"SWC-30 - Lysimeter")
axs["C"].plot(swc30_L2_eco2_sim1[s1:e1], linewidth=1,
    label=r"SWC-30 - $PETc_{+300ppm~CO_2}$", color="#1f77b4",)
axs["C"].plot(swc30_L2_aco2_sim1[s1:e1], linewidth=1, linestyle="--",
    label=r"SWC-30 - $PETc_{ambient}$", color="darkorange",);
axs["C"].set_ylabel("SWC [%]", size=axslabels)
axs["C"].legend(frameon=False, fontsize=legends, loc="lower left", numpoints=3)

# D
axs["D"].plot(seep_L2_lysi[s1:e1], "ko", linewidth=0.1, markersize=1,
↳label=r"Seep. at lysimeter")
    #axs[1, 1].plot(seep_L0_lysi[s1:e1], color="darkorange", marker="x",
↳linewidth=0.1, markersize=1, label=r"Lysimeter L0 seepage")
axs["D"].plot(seep_L2_eco2_sim1[s1:e1], linewidth=1,
    label=r"Seep. $PETc_{eCO_2}$", color="#1f77b4",)
axs["D"].plot(seep_L2_aco2_sim1[s1:e1], linewidth=0.7, linestyle="--",
    label=r"Seep. $PETc_{amb.}$", color="darkorange",)
axs["D"].set_ylabel("Seep. [mm.d$^{-1}$]", size=axslabels)
axs["D"].legend(frameon=False, fontsize=legends, loc="upper left", ncol=3,
↳numpoints=3)

axs["C"].set_yticks([25,30,35,40])
axs["D"].set_yticks([0,1,2,3])

# Set lims and ticks
for key in axs.keys():
    axs[key].set_xlim(pd.Timestamp(s1), pd.Timestamp(e1))
    axs[key].set_xticks([pd.Timestamp("2018-1-1"), pd.Timestamp("2018-7-1"), pd.
↳Timestamp("2019-1-1"),
        pd.Timestamp("2019-7-1"), pd.Timestamp("2020-1-1"), pd.
↳Timestamp("2020-7-1"), pd.Timestamp("2020-12-31")],)
    axs[key].set_xticklabels(["Jan-18", "Jul-18", "Jan-19", "Jul-19", "Jan-20",
↳"Jul-20", ""])

axs["A"].set_ylim(0,1400)
axs["B"].set_ylim(0,160)
axs["D"].set_ylim(0, 4)
axs["C"].set_ylim(20, 45)

# inset_axes for seepage 1
axins = axs["D"].inset_axes([0.1, 0.4, 0.15, 0.33])
s1, e1 = ("2018-10-27", "2018-11-17")
axins.plot(seep_L2_lysi[s1:e1], "ko", linewidth=0.1, markersize=1,
↳label=r"Lysimeter L2 Seep")

```

```

    #axins.plot(seep_L0_lysi[s1:e1], "kx", linewidth=0.1, markersize=1,
    ↪label=r"Lysimeter L0 Seep")
axins.plot(seep_L2_eco2_sim1[s1:e1], linewidth=0.7, label=r"Seep. with
    ↪$ETc_{+300ppm~CO_2}$", color="#1f77b4",)
axins.plot(seep_L2_aco2_sim1[s1:e1], linewidth=0.7, linestyle="--",
    ↪label=r"Seep. with $ETc_{amb}$", color="darkorange",)
axins.fill_between(fluxes_sim[s1:e1].index, fluxes_sim.loc[s1:e1, "s_L2amb_5"],
    ↪fluxes_sim.loc[s1:e1, "s_L2amb_95"],facecolor='orange',zorder=0,
        linewidth=0,label='parameter uncertainty', alpha=0.5)
axins.fill_between(fluxes_sim[s1:e1].index, fluxes_sim.loc[s1:e1,
    ↪"s_L2eco2_5"], fluxes_sim.loc[s1:e1,
    ↪"s_L2eco2_95"],facecolor='blue',zorder=0,
        linewidth=0,label='parameter uncertainty', alpha=0.5)

axins.set_xticks(["2018-10-27", "2018-11-17"])
axins.set_xticklabels(("27.oct", "17.nov"))
axins.tick_params(axis="both", direction="in", labelsize=texts)
axins.set_xlim(pd.Timestamp("2018-10-27"), pd.Timestamp("2018-11-17"))
axins.set_ylim(0, 1)
rect = mpatches.Rectangle((pd.Timestamp("2018-10-17"), -0.14),
pd.Timedelta(34, "D"), 1.14, linewidth=0.4, edgecolor="black",
    ↪facecolor="none", zorder=10,)
axs["D"].add_patch(rect)

# inset_axes for seepage 1
axins = axs["D"].inset_axes([0.44, 0.4, 0.15, 0.33])
s1, e1 = ("2019-10-9", "2019-10-27")
axins.plot(seep_L2_lysi[s1:e1], "ko", linewidth=0.1, markersize=1,
    ↪label=r"Lysimeter L2 Seep")
    #axins.plot(seep_L0_lysi[s1:e1], "kx", linewidth=0.1, markersize=1,
    ↪label=r"Lysimeter L0 Seep")
axins.plot(seep_L2_eco2_sim1[s1:e1], linewidth=0.7, label=r"Seep. with
    ↪$ETc_{+300ppm~CO_2}$", color="#1f77b4",)
axins.plot(seep_L2_aco2_sim1[s1:e1], linewidth=0.7, linestyle="--",
    ↪label=r"Seep. with $ETc_{amb}$", color="darkorange",)
axins.set_xticks(["2019-10-09", "2019-10-27"])
axins.set_xticklabels(("9.oct", "27.oct"))
axins.tick_params(axis="both", direction="in", labelsize=texts)
axins.set_xlim(pd.Timestamp("2019-10-09"), pd.Timestamp("2019-10-27"))
axins.set_ylim(0, 0.5)
rect = mpatches.Rectangle((pd.Timestamp("2019-10-05"), -0.14),
pd.Timedelta(21, "D"), 0.64, linewidth=0.4, edgecolor="black",
    ↪facecolor="none", zorder=10,)
axs["D"].add_patch(rect)
axins.fill_between(fluxes_sim[s1:e1].index, fluxes_sim.loc[s1:e1, "s_L2amb_5"],
    ↪fluxes_sim.loc[s1:e1, "s_L2amb_95"],facecolor='orange',zorder=0,

```

```

        linewidth=0,label='parameter uncertainty', alpha=0.5)
axins.fill_between(fluxes_sim[s1:e1].index, fluxes_sim.loc[s1:e1,
↳"s_L2eco2_5"], fluxes_sim.loc[s1:e1,
↳"s_L2eco2_95"],facecolor='blue',zorder=0,
        linewidth=0,label='parameter uncertainty', alpha=0.5)

# inset_axes for seepage 2
axins = axs["D"].inset_axes([0.78, 0.4, 0.15, 0.33])
s1, e1 = ("2020-07-01", "2020-07-17")
axins.plot(seep_L2_lysi[s1:e1], "ko", linewidth=0.1, markersize=1,
↳label=r"Lysimeter L2 Seep")
    #axins.plot(seep_L0_lysi[s1:e1], "kx", linewidth=0.1, markersize=1,
↳label=r"Lysimeter L0 Seep")
axins.plot(seep_L2_eco2_sim1[s1:e1], linewidth=0.7, label=r"Seep. with
↳$ETc_{+300ppm-CO_2}$", color="#1f77b4",)
axins.plot(seep_L2_aco2_sim1[s1:e1], linewidth=0.7, linestyle="--",
↳label=r"Seep. with $ETc_{amb}$", color="darkorange",)
axins.set_xticks([s1,e1])
axins.set_xticklabels(("1.jul", "17.jul"))
axins.tick_params(axis="both", direction="in", labelsize=texts)
axins.set_xlim(pd.Timestamp(s1), pd.Timestamp(e1))
axins.set_ylim(0, 0.5)
rect = mpatches.Rectangle((pd.Timestamp("2020-6-27"), -0.14),
pd.Timedelta(21, "D"), 0.64, linewidth=0.4, edgecolor="black",
↳facecolor="none", zorder=10,)
axs["D"].add_patch(rect)
axins.fill_between(fluxes_sim[s1:e1].index, fluxes_sim.loc[s1:e1, "s_L2amb_5"],
↳fluxes_sim.loc[s1:e1, "s_L2amb_95"],facecolor='orange',zorder=0,
        linewidth=0,label='parameter uncertainty', alpha=0.5)
axins.fill_between(fluxes_sim[s1:e1].index, fluxes_sim.loc[s1:e1,
↳"s_L2eco2_5"], fluxes_sim.loc[s1:e1,
↳"s_L2eco2_95"],facecolor='blue',zorder=0,
        linewidth=0,label='parameter uncertainty', alpha=0.5)
fig.text(0.49,0.94,"a", fontsize=7)
fig.text(0.935,0.94,"b", fontsize=7)
fig.text(0.49,0.475,"c", fontsize=7)
fig.text(0.935,0.475,"d", fontsize=7)
plt.subplots_adjust(hspace=0, wspace=0, right=0.95, left=0.06, top=0.97,
↳bottom=0.04)
#fig.savefig("figures/figure9.png", dpi=300)

```


7 Modelling 1990-2020

```
[49]: meteo_Irdning = pd.read_csv( "data\\Irdning_hourly_19900101_20201231.csv",
↳index_col="time",parse_dates=True,)
```

```
[50]: meteo_Aigen = pd.read_csv( "data\\Aigen_hourly_19900101_20201231.csv",
↳index_col="time",parse_dates=True,)
```

```
[51]: meteo_grob = pd.read_csv( "data\\Groebming1_19900101_20201231.csv",
↳index_col="time",parse_dates=True,)
```

```
[52]: meteo_1990_2020 = meteo_Irdning.copy()
meteo_1990_2020.loc["1990", "GSX"] = meteo_grob.loc["1990", "GSX"]
meteo_1990_2020.loc["1991-9", "GSX"] = meteo_grob.loc["1991-9", "GSX"]
meteo_1990_2020.loc[meteo_1990_2020["GSX"].isna(), "GSX"] = meteo_Aigen.loc[
    meteo_Irdning["GSX"].isna(), "GSX"]
meteo_1990_2020.loc[meteo_1990_2020["GSX"].isna(), "GSX"] = meteo_grob.loc[
    meteo_Irdning["GSX"].isna(), "GSX"]
```

```
[53]: meteo_1990_2020.loc["2006-1-15":"2006-2-16", "FFX"] = meteo_Aigen.
↳loc["2006-1-15":"2006-2-16", "FFX"]
meteo_1990_2020.loc["2006-4-26":"2006-5-7", "FFX"] = meteo_Aigen.
↳loc["2006-4-26":"2006-5-7", "FFX"]
meteo_1990_2020.loc["2006-12-11":"2007-3-11", "FFX"] = meteo_Aigen.
↳loc["2006-12-11":"2007-3-11", "FFX"]
meteo_1990_2020.loc["1990-6-20":"1990-6-29", "FFX"] = meteo_grob.
↳loc["1990-6-20":"1990-6-29", "FFX"]
meteo_1990_2020.loc["1990-6-3", "FFX"] = meteo_grob.loc["1990-6-3", "FFX"]
meteo_1990_2020.loc["1998-6-16":"1998-6-21", "FFX"] = meteo_Aigen.
↳loc["1998-6-16":"1998-6-21", "FFX"]
```

```
meteo_1990_2020.loc["1999-5-12":"1999-5-20", "FFX"] = meteo_Aigen.
↳loc["1999-5-12":"1999-5-20", "FFX"]
meteo_1990_2020.loc["2007-6-24":"2007-7-6", "FFX"] = meteo_Aigen.
↳loc["2007-6-24":"2007-7-6", "FFX"]
```

```
[54]: meteo_1990_2020.loc["2006-1-10":"2006-5-10", "RSX"] = meteo_Aigen.
↳loc["2006-1-10":"2006-5-10", "RSX"]
meteo_1990_2020.loc["2014-1-10":"2014-2-25", "VVX"] = meteo_Aigen.
↳loc["2014-1-10":"2014-2-25", "VVX"]
meteo_1990_2020.loc["2006-1-10":"2006-2-20", "VVX"] = meteo_Aigen.
↳loc["2006-1-10":"2006-2-20", "VVX"]
meteo_1990_2020.loc["2006-4-20":"2006-5-10", "VVX"] = meteo_Aigen.
↳loc["2006-4-20":"2006-5-10", "VVX"]
```

```
[55]: meteo_1990_2020 = meteo_1990_2020.interpolate()
```

```
[56]: meteo_1990_2020.plot(subplots=True, figsize=(19, 15))
```

```
[56]: array([<AxesSubplot:xlabel='time'>, <AxesSubplot:xlabel='time'>,
<AxesSubplot:xlabel='time'>, <AxesSubplot:xlabel='time'>,
<AxesSubplot:xlabel='time'>, <AxesSubplot:xlabel='time'>],
dtype=object)
```



```
[57]: tmax = meteo_1990_2020["TTX"].resample("d").max()
tmin = meteo_1990_2020["TTX"].resample("d").min()
tmean = meteo_1990_2020["TTX"].resample("d").mean()
rhmax = meteo_1990_2020["FFX"].resample("d").max()
rhmin = meteo_1990_2020["FFX"].resample("d").min()
rhmean = meteo_1990_2020["FFX"].resample("d").mean()
wind = meteo_1990_2020["VVX"].resample("d").mean()
rglobal = meteo_1990_2020["GSX"].resample("d").sum() / 100
precip = meteo_1990_2020["RSX"].resample("d").sum()
meteo_1990_2020_d = pd.DataFrame(
    {"tmax": tmax, "tmin": tmin, "tmean": tmean,
     "rhmax": rhmax, "rhmin": rhmin, "rhmean": rhmean,
     "wind": wind, "rglobal": rglobal, "precip": precip,})
```

```
[58]: print(tmax[tmax.isnull()])
print(rhmax[rhmax.isnull()])
print(wind[wind.isnull()])
print(rglobal[rglobal.isnull()])
print(precip[precip.isnull()])
```

```
Series([], Freq: D, Name: TTX, dtype: float64)
Series([], Freq: D, Name: FFX, dtype: float64)
Series([], Freq: D, Name: VVX, dtype: float64)
Series([], Freq: D, Name: GSX, dtype: float64)
Series([], Freq: D, Name: RSX, dtype: float64)
```

```
[59]: def et_sc2(r_l, lai, croph):
    pe = pyet.pm(
        tmean,
        wind,
        rglobal,
        elevation=elevation,
        lat=lat,
        rhmax=rhmax,
        rhmin=rhmin,
        rh=rhmean,
        tmax=tmax,
        tmin=tmin,
        lai=lai,
        croph=croph,
        r_l=r_l,
        a=1,
        b=0,
        lai_eff=0,
        ra_method=2,
```

```
)  
return pe
```

8 SPEI index

```
[60]: precip_m = precip.resample("m").sum()  
et_m = pyet.pm_fao56(tmean, wind, rglobal, elevation=elevation, lat=lat,  
                    rhmax=rhmax, rhmin=rhmin, rh=rhmean, tmax=tmax, tmin=tmin,  
                    a=1, b=0,).resample("m").sum()
```

```
[61]: from climate_indices import indices  
from climate_indices.compute import scale_values, Periodicity
```

```
[62]: spei = indices.spei(precip_m.values, et_m.values, scale=1,  
                        distribution=indices.Distribution.gamma,  
                        data_start_year=1990, calibration_year_initial=1991,  
                        calibration_year_final=2020,  
                        periodicity=Periodicity.monthly,)
```

```
[63]: df = pd.DataFrame({"precip":precip_m, "pet":et_m, "spei":spei})
```

```
[64]: axslabels = 5  
xylabels = 4  
legends = 5  
texts = 5  
  
fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(figw_1c * cm, 2.8 * cm), dpi=300, ncols=1)  
ax.axhline(0, color="k", linestyle="--", alpha=0.4)  
ax.plot(df.loc[:, "spei"])  
ax.set_ylabel("SPEI [-]", fontsize=axslabels)  
ax.set_xlabel("")  
ax.set_xlim(pd.Timestamp("1991-1-1"), pd.Timestamp("2020-12-31"))  
plt.tight_layout()
```


9 Scenarios:

9.1 2050

2100

```
[65]: s1, e1 = ("1990", "2020")
et_rcp3 = et_sc2(65 * (1 + 0.002 * (420 - 300)), 2.3, 0.25)[s1:e1]
et_rcp45 = et_sc2(65 * (1 + 0.002 * (538 - 300)), 2.3, 0.25)[s1:e1]
et_rcp6 = et_sc2(65 * (1 + 0.002 * (670 - 300)), 2.3, 0.25)[s1:e1]
et_rcp85 = et_sc2(65 * (1 + 0.002 * (935 - 300)), 2.3, 0.25)[s1:e1]
```

```
[66]: s1, e1 = ("2018", "2018")
et_rcp3[s1:e1].plot(figsize=(16, 4), color="blue")
et_rcp45[s1:e1].plot(figsize=(16, 4))
et_rcp6[s1:e1].plot(figsize=(16, 4))
et_rcp85[s1:e1].plot(figsize=(16, 4), color="red")
```

```
[66]: <AxesSubplot:xlabel='time'>
```



```
[67]: s1, e1 = ("1990", "1990")
et_rcp3[s1:e1].cumsum().plot(figsize=(16, 4))
et_rcp45[s1:e1].cumsum().plot(figsize=(16, 4))
et_rcp6[s1:e1].cumsum().plot(figsize=(16, 4))
et_rcp85[s1:e1].cumsum().plot(figsize=(16, 4))
precip[s1:e1].cumsum().plot(figsize=(16, 4))
```

```
[67]: <AxesSubplot:xlabel='time'>
```


10 Hydrus simulation

```
[68]: def run_hydrus(name, prec, tmean, root, rsoil, soil_params,
↳s1="1990", e1="2020"):
    # Hydrus model
    exe = os.path.join(os.getcwd(), "hydrus_co2.exe")
    m1 = ps.Model(
        exe_name=exe,
        ws_name=name,
        name="model",
        mass_units="mmol",
        time_unit="days",
        length_unit="cm",
    )
    m1.basic_info["lSnow"] = True
    m1.basic_info["lTemp"] = True

    m1.add_time_info(tinit=0, tmax=len(prec[s1:e1]), dtmin=1e-4,
↳print_times=True)
    m1.add_waterflow(top_bc=2, bot_bc=4)
    m = m1.get_empty_material_df(n=3)
    m.loc[[1,2,3]] = soil_params
    m1.add_material(m)

    h = m1.get_empty_heat_df()
    h.loc[[1,2,3]] = heat_params
    m1.add_heat_transport(
        h, amp1=0, top_bc=1, bot_bc=1, top_temp=5, bot_temp=10, icampbell=1
    )
    nodes = 140 # Discretize soil column into n elements
    depth = [-25, -90, -140] # [-30, -100, -140] # Depth of the soil column
    profile = ps.create_profile(bot=depth, dx=abs(depth[-1] / nodes), mat=1)
    d1, d2 = get_idx_from_depth(depth[0], profile),
↳get_idx_from_depth(depth[1], profile)
```

```

profile.loc[d1:d2, "Mat"] = 2
profile.loc[d2:141, "Mat"] = 3
profile["Beta"] = roots(profile["x"], 10, 20)
profile["Temp"] = np.linspace(stemp.loc["2017-1-1", "temp_5cm_L2"], stemp.
↳loc["2017-1-1", "temp_140cm_L2"], 141)
profile["h"] = np.linspace(-25, -15, 141) # Determine initial Pressure Head
ml.add_profile(profile) # Add the profile

bc = {
    "tAtm": np.arange(len(prec[s1:e1])) + 1,
    "Prec": np.asarray(prec[s1:e1]),
    "tTop": np.asarray(tmean[s1:e1]),
    "tBot": np.ones(len(tmean[s1:e1])),
    "rSoil": np.asarray(rsoil[s1:e1]),
    "rRoot": np.asarray(rroot[s1:e1]),
}
atm = pd.DataFrame(bc, index=np.arange(len(prec[s1:e1])))
ml.add_atmospheric_bc(atm, hcrits=0) # , hcrita=10e8
ml.add_obs_nodes([-30])
ml.add_root_uptake(model=1, poptm=[-25, -25, -25], p50=-400)
ml.write_input() # Write input
ml.simulate()
vroot = ml.read_alevel()["sum(vRoot)"].diff()[365:] * 10
seep = (ml.read_alevel()["sum(vBot)"] * -1).diff()[365:]
swc30 = ml.read_obs_node()[31]["theta"][366:] * 100
vroot.index = prec["1991:].index
seep.index = prec["1991:].index
swc30.index = prec["1991:].index
return ml, vroot, seep, swc30

```

```

[69]: print(precip[precip.isnull()])
print(tmean[tmean.isnull()])
print(et_rcp3[et_rcp3.isnull()])

```

```

Series([], Freq: D, Name: RSX, dtype: float64)
Series([], Freq: D, Name: TTX, dtype: float64)
Series([], Freq: D, dtype: float64)

```

```

[70]: s1, e1 = ("1990", "2020")
rsoil_rcp3 = et_rcp3[s1:e1] * np.exp(-0.6 * 2.5) / 10 # cm/d
rroot_rcp3 = et_rcp3[s1:e1] * (1 - np.exp(-0.6 * 2.5)) / 10 # cm/d
rroot_rcp45 = et_rcp45[s1:e1] * (1 - np.exp(-0.6 * 2.5)) / 10 # cm/d
rroot_rcp6 = et_rcp6[s1:e1] * (1 - np.exp(-0.6 * 2.5)) / 10 # cm/d
rroot_rcp85 = et_rcp85[s1:e1] * (1 - np.exp(-0.6 * 2.5)) / 10 # cm/d

```

```

[71]: ml_rcp3_L0, vroot_rcp3_L0, seep_rcp3_L0, swc_rcp3_L0 = run_hydrus("L2_rcp3",
↳precip / 10, tmean, rroot_rcp3, rsoil_rcp3, soil_par_L0)

```

```

ml_rcp45_L0, vroot_rcp45_L0, seep_rcp45_L0, swc_rcp45_L0 =
↳run_hydrus("L2_rcp45", precip / 10, tmean, rroot_rcp45, rsoil_rcp3,
↳soil_par_L0)
ml_rcp6_L0, vroot_rcp6_L0, seep_rcp6_L0, swc_rcp6_L0 = run_hydrus("L2_rcp6",
↳precip / 10, tmean, rroot_rcp6, rsoil_rcp3, soil_par_L0)
ml_rcp85_L0, vroot_rcp85_L0, seep_rcp85_L0, swc_rcp85_L0 = run_hydrus(
↳"L2_rcp85", precip / 10, tmean, rroot_rcp85, rsoil_rcp3, soil_par_L0)

ml_rcp3_L2, vroot_rcp3_L2, seep_rcp3_L2, swc_rcp3_L2 = run_hydrus("L2_rcp3",
↳precip / 10, tmean, rroot_rcp3, rsoil_rcp3, soil_par_L2)
ml_rcp45_L2, vroot_rcp45_L2, seep_rcp45_L2, swc_rcp45_L2 =
↳run_hydrus("L2_rcp45", precip / 10, tmean, rroot_rcp45, rsoil_rcp3,
↳soil_par_L2)
ml_rcp6_L2, vroot_rcp6_L2, seep_rcp6_L2, swc_rcp6_L2 = run_hydrus("L2_rcp6",
↳precip / 10, tmean, rroot_rcp6, rsoil_rcp3, soil_par_L2)
ml_rcp85_L2, vroot_rcp85_L2, seep_rcp85_L2, swc_rcp85_L2 = run_hydrus(
↳"L2_rcp85", precip / 10, tmean, rroot_rcp85, rsoil_rcp3, soil_par_L2)

```

```

[72]: seep_rcp3_L2.cumsum().plot()
seep_rcp6_L2.cumsum().plot()
seep_rcp85_L2.cumsum().plot()

```

```
[72]: <AxesSubplot:xlabel='time'>
```



```

[73]: # co2 levels relative to
fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(figw_1c * cm, 1.3), dpi=300)
labels = ["+118", "+250", "+515"]
data = [(et_rcp45["1991:"].resample("y").sum() - et_rcp3["1991:"].
→resample("y").sum())
        / et_rcp3["1991:"].resample("y").sum()
        * 100).values,
        ((et_rcp6["1991:"].resample("y").sum() - et_rcp3["1991:"].resample("y").
→sum())
        / et_rcp3["1991:"].resample("y").sum()
        * 100).dropna().values]
data2 = [(vroot_rcp45_L0.resample("y").sum() - vroot_rcp3_L0.resample("y").
→sum()) / vroot_rcp3_L0.resample("y").sum()* 100).values,
        (vroot_rcp45_L2.resample("y").sum() - vroot_rcp3_L2.resample("y").
→sum()) / vroot_rcp3_L2.resample("y").sum()* 100).values,
        (vroot_rcp6_L0.resample("y").sum() - vroot_rcp3_L0.resample("y").
→sum()) / vroot_rcp3_L0.resample("y").sum()* 100).values,
        (vroot_rcp6_L2.resample("y").sum() - vroot_rcp3_L2.resample("y").
→sum()) / vroot_rcp3_L2.resample("y").sum()* 100).values,]
data3 = [(seep_rcp45_L0.resample("y").sum() - seep_rcp3_L0.resample("y").
→sum()) / seep_rcp3_L0.resample("y").sum() * 100).values,
        (seep_rcp45_L2.resample("y").sum() - seep_rcp3_L2.resample("y").
→sum()) / seep_rcp3_L2.resample("y").sum() * 100).values,
        ((seep_rcp6_L0.resample("y").sum() - seep_rcp3_L0.resample("y").sum())
→/ seep_rcp3_L0.resample("y").sum()* 100).values,
        ((seep_rcp6_L2.resample("y").sum() - seep_rcp3_L2.resample("y").sum())
→/ seep_rcp3_L2.resample("y").sum()* 100).values,]

medianprops = dict(linestyle='-', linewidth=0.5)
flierprops = dict(marker='o', markerfacecolor="none", markersize=2,
                  markeredgewidth=0.4)
boxprops = dict(linestyle='-', linewidth=0.5, facecolor="white")
whiskerprops = dict(linestyle='-', linewidth=0.5)
capprops = dict(linestyle='-', linewidth=0.5)
bplot = ax.boxplot(np.concatenate((data, data2, data3)).T,
                  positions=[1, 1.8,
                              2.6, 3.0, 3.8, 4.2,
                              5.0, 5.4, 6.2, 6.6], widths=0.25,
                  flierprops=flierprops, boxprops=boxprops, medianprops=medianprops,
                  whiskerprops=whiskerprops, capprops=capprops, patch_artist=True)
colors=["", "",
        "", "////////", "", "////////",
        "", "////////", "-", "////////",]
x=0
for patch in bplot['boxes']:
    # patch.set_hatch(colors[x])

```

```

    patch.set(hatch = colors[x])
    x += 1
ax.set_xticks([1, 1.8, 2.8, 4.0, 5.2, 6.4])
ax.xaxis.set_ticklabels(["RCP4.5\n+118", "RCP6.0\n+250"]*3)
ax.axhline(0, linestyle="--", lw=0.4, zorder=0, color="k")
fig.text(0.095, 0.81, "        Potential \n evapotranspiration", fontsize=5.75)
fig.text(0.34, 0.88, "        Actual transpiration", fontsize=5.75)
fig.text(0.765, 0.88, "Seepage", fontsize=5.75)
ax.set_ylim(-10,40)
ax.set_xlabel(r"$CO_2$ [ppm]", fontsize=6)
ax.set_ylabel("Relative change [%]", fontsize=6)
for vk in (2.1, 4.6):
    ax.axvline(vk, color="k", linestyle="-.", alpha=0.5)
ax.tick_params(axis='both', labelsize=5.5)
plt.tight_layout()
plt.subplots_adjust(bottom=0.25, left=0.09, right=0.99, top=0.95)
circ1 = mpatches.Patch( facecolor="None",edgecolor="k",
    ↪hatch=r'\\\\\\',label=r'$eCO_2$', linewidth=0.5)
circ2 = mpatches.Patch( facecolor="None", edgecolor="k", label='ambient',
    ↪linewidth=0.5)

ax.legend(handles = [circ2,circ1],loc="center", facecolor="white",
    ↪shadow=False, framealpha=0, fontsize=texts)
#fig.savefig("figures/figure8.png", dpi=300)

```

[73]: <matplotlib.legend.Legend at 0x1bfe7ae19a0>


```

[74]: print((((seep_rcp6_L0.resample("y").sum() - seep_rcp3_L0.resample("y").sum()) /
    ↪seep_rcp3_L0.resample("y").sum()* 100).values).max())
print((((seep_rcp6_L0.resample("y").sum() - seep_rcp3_L0.resample("y").sum()) /
    ↪seep_rcp3_L0.resample("y").sum()* 100).values).min())
print((((seep_rcp6_L2.resample("y").sum() - seep_rcp3_L2.resample("y").sum()) /
    ↪seep_rcp3_L2.resample("y").sum()* 100).values).max())
print((((seep_rcp6_L2.resample("y").sum() - seep_rcp3_L2.resample("y").sum()) /
    ↪seep_rcp3_L2.resample("y").sum()* 100).values).min())

```

24.48146888813323
3.5722473479085517
15.34231722428791
3.069295271553288

```
[75]: print(((vroot_rcp6_L0.resample("y").sum() - vroot_rcp3_L0.resample("y").sum())  
      ↪ / vroot_rcp3_L0.resample("y").sum()* 100).values).max())  
print(((vroot_rcp6_L0.resample("y").sum() - vroot_rcp3_L0.resample("y").sum())  
      ↪ / vroot_rcp3_L0.resample("y").sum()* 100).values).min())  
print(((vroot_rcp6_L2.resample("y").sum() - vroot_rcp3_L2.resample("y").sum())  
      ↪ / vroot_rcp3_L2.resample("y").sum()* 100).values).max())  
print(((vroot_rcp6_L2.resample("y").sum() - vroot_rcp3_L2.resample("y").sum())  
      ↪ / vroot_rcp3_L2.resample("y").sum()* 100).values).min())
```

-2.535731751565736
-5.998082318264208
-1.94738703851942
-5.93745525944413